

The Economics and Ethics of Requiring 150 Semester Hours of Coursework to Sit for the CPA Exam

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Abstract

Most "Who Do You Trust?" surveys rank politicians, lawyers and used car salesmen at the bottom and certified public accountants at the top. That is because the CPA profession has a squeaky clean image. CPAs are known and respected for their honesty. The profession goes out of its way to project that image, and there is a certain amount of truth to it.

But there is one area where the CPA profession has fallen far short of protecting the public interest -- the regulation of accounting education. Like just about all the other trades and professions, CPAs have morally bankrupted themselves by going to the various state legislatures to ask for protection against competitors. Worse yet, they do it claiming to protect the public interest.

In this article, the author discusses some economic and ethical issues relating to the requirement that candidates must have 150 semester hours of credit to sit for the certified public accountant exam.

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Most "Who Do You Trust?" surveys rank politicians, lawyers and used car salesmen at the bottom and certified public accountants at the top. That is because the CPA profession has a squeaky clean image -- anal retentive little wimps who wear thick glasses and can't get a date. CPAs are known and respected for their honesty. The profession goes out of its way to project that image, and there is a certain amount of truth to it. And they aren't all anal retentive little wimps who can't get a date. Many of them are quite articulate. Some of them are quite lovely (in some schools, more than half of the accounting majors are women).

But there is one area where the CPA profession has fallen far short of protecting the public interest -- the regulation of accounting education. Like just about all the other trades and professions, CPAs have morally bankrupted themselves by going to the various state legislatures to ask for protection against competitors. Worse yet, they do it claiming to protect the public interest.

How did this moral bankruptcy come about? A few years ago the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA), the largest CPA membership organization in the world, presently located in Jersey City, New Jersey, decided that starting in the year 2000, new members would have to have 150 semester hours of college credits (5 years) instead of the present four years to become a member. On the surface, that doesn't appear to be any big deal. No one has to become an AICPA member to practice public accounting or to be a CPA. But the story doesn't stop there.

The AICPA has made a concerted effort to make it a requirement to have five years of college before being allowed to sit for the CPA exam. CPA Exam requirements are somewhat different in each state and the various state legislatures determine what the rules are for their state. So the AICPA started working in conjunction with the CPA societies in each state to lobby their legislatures to make 150 semester hours a requirement.

Their argument for making this requirement seems plausible on the surface. Financial reporting requirements and the tax law have become so complex that accountants can't learn

enough in just four years to do a competent job when they graduate. So the solution is to require a fifth year of college. However, there are several problems with this argument. For example, present accreditation rules require accounting majors to take about 75 percent of their coursework in fields other than accounting -- 50 percent in liberal arts and 25 in other business areas. Accounting majors could easily take more accounting courses if only they were able to cut back on their liberal arts requirement. But they can't do that because the accreditors won't allow it. The six regional accreditation agencies have a monopoly on their region of the country, so schools that offer accounting programs don't have any choice but to accept whatever rules these accreditation agencies dictate. If they try to offer an accounting program that is more consumer-oriented they risk losing their accreditation.

Not only do the professional CPA associations not try to break up this accreditation monopoly; they support it and advocate going a step further. While they would require a fifth year of college work in order to sit for the CPA exam, many of them would not require any additional accounting courses. They want accounting students to take more liberal arts courses. They want students to be more well-rounded than they are now. Advocates argue that students can learn the accounting they couldn't get in school by working in the profession, but somehow they can't become more well-rounded after they leave school.

It is amazing that these otherwise rational CPAs could believe such poppycock, much less foist it onto the rest of us. Many (but not all) state legislatures have bought this argument hook, line and sinker, and have passed laws making it a requirement to complete 150 semester hours of coursework, much of it of nebulous quality or relevance, in order to sit for the CPA exam starting in the year 2000.

What effect will this legislation have? Who will be harmed and who will be helped? The most obvious group harmed is the students (or parents) who must cough up another \$10,000 or \$20,000 for a fifth year of education. Then there is the opportunity

cost of not having a job for the extra year it will take to complete the fifth year, so there's another \$25-30,000.

But that's not the end of it. The segment of the student population most harmed by this insane policy is the segment least likely to be able to pay for a fifth year -- blacks, hispanics, and low-income students of whatever persuasion. This is why Jesse Jackson and some black groups have opposed this requirement. Poor people and minorities, along with the rest of us, will have to face an even higher barrier to entry into the accounting profession.

Consumers of accounting services also stand to be harmed. It is a basic law of economics that if you raise the price of something by 25 percent, less of it will be demanded. There will be fewer CPAs in the future because the cost of becoming a CPA has been artificially increased by at least 25 percent, not counting the opportunity cost of being off the job market for an additional year. As the supply of CPAs is cut back, the price that existing CPAs can charge will go up. Thus, those who are already CPAs -- the ones who are going to the various state legislatures for protection -- are, in effect, feathering their own nest at the expense of the general public. As the price of CPA services goes up, smaller businesses will be especially harmed because they cannot afford the extent of service they could buy in the past. Publicly traded companies will also have to pay more for the same level of service. If they try to cut costs, they may have to be content with a lower level of service. Or they could maintain the level of accounting services they receive and try to pass on the extra cost to the consumers who buy their products. Or they could hire fewer employees or give existing employees lower annual raises to compensate for their higher costs.

If the CPA profession were really concerned with serving the public interest, there are a number of things it could do. One suggestion that has been put forth is to insist that the six regional accreditation agencies have special rules for accounting majors. Accounting students should not be forced to take 50 percent of their program in liberal arts if they cannot learn enough accounting in four years to be good practitioners. Since the monopolistic six

regional agencies probably will not buy into that rule change, the accounting profession should be prepared to form its own accreditation agency, just like the medical and legal professions have done.

The problem with this proposal is that the medical and legal accreditation agencies have not always worked in the public interest, either. They have at times adopted policies that merely raise the cost of a medical or legal education with little or no benefit to the public.

A better solution, one that would be more likely to protect the public interest and not act to feather the nest of current practitioners at the expense of the general public, would be to let the market decide what kind of education accountants should receive. If the CPA exam really does measure someone's competence in accounting, why not ABOLISH all formal education requirements and let anyone take the exam? It is highly unlikely that anyone who does not know a lot of accounting will be able to pass the exam. I know. I took it. If someone knows enough accounting to pass the exam, why not award them the CPA certificate? They have earned it. If employers think that their CPAs should also have a liberal arts background they can refuse to hire anyone who does not have one.

If this proposal were implemented, the cost of accounting education would drop considerably -- by 75 percent or more -- since potential CPAs would only have to take about 30 or 36 hours of coursework to prepare for the exam instead of the 120 -- 150 they now have to take. If having a liberal arts background or five years of college has some value to the marketplace, then accountants who have this kind of background will advance faster and further than those who don't have it. Let the market -- consumers -- decide, not politicians and the accounting establishment.